

Pyrazine Condensations from Malononitrile

JOE V. D'SOUZA*

Department of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology, Madras-600 036

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Tetrasubstituted pyrazines and pyridinopyrazines are rare to find or obtain. This paper reports that they are obtained from malononitrile. They can be modified at will for use in medicine. Two reactions are proposed for obtaining the highly basic intermediate II which is highly reactive to yield pyrazines.

PYRAZINES now find increasing application in dye chemistry¹⁻³ and in medicinal chemistry^{4,5}.

Among diuretics, the pteridines and pyrazines (amiloride) have shown high natriuretic but little kaliuretic effect⁶⁻¹¹. The products of this work have been tested unsuccessfully in diuresis and against diabetes. Tetrasubstituted pyrazines are rare but show excellent tridentate liganding properties.

Experimental

Preparation of 2-aza-1,1,3,3-tetracyanopropane (II):

Method A: The method of Wallenfels¹² was used. 25 g malononitrile was converted to the oxime¹³ (ν_{max} 3000, 2200, 1700 cm^{-1} ; δ (D_2O) 1.9 ppm DOH 4.9 ppm methylene). Oximinomalononitrile was converted to the tosylate¹⁴ (yellow-pink powder, m.p. 118°; ν_{max} 2240, 1580, 1300 cm^{-1}). The sodium salt of malononitrile was prepared with molecular sodium in benzene. After the reaction the method of separation was as outlined below.

Method B: 25 g malononitrile was converted to oximinomalononitrile¹³ and taken in 300 ml dry benzene. To it was added 25 g malononitrile and the mixture heated on a water bath and 5 ml piperidine and 5 ml acetic acid were added with stirring. Water was removed with a Dean and Stark apparatus. After removal of 100 ml benzene, vacuum was applied and benzene completely removed. Separation of the product was done as outlined below.

Separation of 2-aza-1,1,3,3-tetracyanopropane (II): The residual thick brown product of Method A or B was chilled and treated with solid Na_2CO_3 till effervescence ceased. It was then extracted with 200 ml ether and the ether extract discarded. The residue was treated with a saturated acetone solution of 30 g mercuric chloride and the thick brown precipitate was filtered under vacuum and washed repeatedly with chilled acetone. A grey brown gel obtained was dried in a desiccator, m.p. $>300^\circ$; ν_{max} 1290 cm^{-1} (C—Hg—C).

The grey brown complex was taken in a three-necked round bottom flask connected with a funnel, stirrer and condenser with rubber tube exiting into a beaker of water. The flask was cooled in an ice bath and 30 g potassium cyanide in 200 ml acetone was added in aliquots. The ice-bath was removed and stirring continued for 1 h more. The flask was then connected to vacuum and acetone removed completely. The residue was extracted with 100 ml portions of ether five times and the combined ether extracts was dried under vacuum. The whole apparatus was then flushed with nitrogen and cooled. The bright yellow crystals separated were dried in a vacuum desiccator and recrystallised from methanol under nitrogen atmosphere, m.p. 98°; ν_{max} 2210, 2200, 1480 cm^{-1} .

Preparation of 2,6-dicyano-3-amino-5-chloropyrazine (III): 1.8 g of II was cyclised with HCl/acetone under reflux for 10 min¹⁵. The solution was chilled to obtain a precipitate. It was crystallised from ethanol to yield orange crystals decomposing after 3 days in air (45%); m.p. 245° (Found: C, 40.4; H, 0.94; N, 39; Cl, 19.6%); ν_{max} 3380, 3300, 2200, 1625 (NH_2), 2950, 1540 cm^{-1} (CN); aromatic n.m.r. in DMF or CF_3COOH shows no peak indicative of C-hydrogens; m/e 179, 125, 152 and 144.

Preparation of 2,7-dicyano-3-methoxy-6,8-diaminopyridino-pyrazine (IV): 15 g of II was treated with 8.7 g sodium salt of malononitrile in 50 ml methanol and the mixture refluxed for 3 h. The flask was then chilled and the precipitate washed with methanol and ether. The crude was dissolved in DMF and reprecipitated with ether on cooling. The precipitate was filtered and dried to yield golden yellow crystals (70%), m.p. 312° (d); turned to red in 3 days; soluble in acetic acid, DMF, DMSO and insoluble in ether, water; ν_{max} 3400, 3300, 3340 (NH_2), 2200, 1625 (CN), 2950 cm^{-1} (aromatic); δ (DMF or CF_3COOH) 4.38 (OCH_3), 7.6 and 8.2 (N protons) when taken in CF_3COOH ; m/e 241, 210.

* Jesuit House, Panaji-403 001.

Another method of preparation of IV: 8.6 g of sodium salt of malononitrile in 30 ml methanol were treated with 20 g tosylate of oximinomalononitrile and refluxed for 3 h. The method of separation of IV was as given above; overall yield, 55%.

Results and Discussion

According to the original method¹²⁻¹⁷ of synthesis the sodium salt of malononitrile was reacted with nitrosotosylate of the same malononitrile

(dicyanomethane or propanedinitrile) to give product II which can easily be cyclised. Another method that we have used for the first time in this reaction is the Knoevenagel reaction. This reaction is being increasingly made use of in malononitrile chemistry¹⁸⁻¹⁹, and use of piperidine or Triton-B brought about high yields and eliminated many preparatory steps in the procedure. The use of phase transfer catalysts, TBAC or 18-crown-6 did not show any advantage over the use of piperidine.

Condensations are not uncommon in the chemistry of malononitrile²¹⁻²⁵ even though the starting material and products are often water sensitive. The substituents in the pyrazine system proved liable²⁰ and this admits of a variety of reactions on the products of our syntheses. The method of separation of II and the compound IV have not been reported earlier.

Ir and nmr data obtained by lagging the preparation of IV over 3 days at 0° indicate the formation of an imido-ester as an intermediate in the reaction. Spectral data also suggest the presence of iminotautomers in the final pyrazine products - the presence in each case of a strong band in the 1660 cm⁻¹ region. The pyrazine absorptions can be assigned to 1580, 1550-30, 1470, 1380-50 cm⁻¹.

Materials : Malononitrile used was of B.D.H. or E. Merck. Ir spectra were recorded on a P. E. 257 spectrophotometer. Nmr spectra were recorded on a Varian XL 100 FT spectrometer. Mass spectra were recorded on a Varian Mat I.

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